

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.21128694

Role Of Flavonoids In Sepsis: Advances And Future Prospects

Sara Osman^{1*}, Ahmad Zorin Sahlan¹, Mazlyzam Bin Abdul Latif¹,

¹Department of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences, National University of Malaysia (UKM), 53100 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

*Corresponding author: osma.sara20@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Sepsis is a life-threatening syndrome caused by a dysregulated host response to infection and is a leading cause of organ failure and death in intensive care units (Singer et al., 2016). Despite advances in critical care, no specific immunomodulatory drug has yet been approved for sepsis treatment (Chen & Wei, 2021). Flavonoids, a diverse class of polyphenolic compounds abundant in fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants, exhibit potent immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and organ protective effects in preclinical sepsis models (Kumar & Pandey, 2013; Panche et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2019). This review synthesizes current evidence on the therapeutic potential of major flavonoids including baicalin, scutellarin, silymarin, luteolin, quercetin, isorhamnetin, fisetin, myricetin, and epigallocatechin 3 gallate in targeting key pathological mechanisms of sepsis. We summarize their molecular mechanisms of action, with emphasis on modulation of NF κ B, MAPK, and Nrf2 signalling pathways, regulation of cytokine production, attenuation of oxidative stress, preservation of endothelial function, and protection against multiple organ dysfunction (Heim et al., 2002; Pietta, 2000; Williams et al., 2004). We also highlight critical barriers to clinical translation, particularly poor oral bioavailability, incomplete pharmacokinetic characterization, and the challenge of timing immunomodulatory interventions within the dynamic course of sepsis (Zhao et al., 2019). Finally, we outline future research priorities, including development of advanced delivery systems, rigorous pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic studies, and carefully designed clinical trials that integrate immune phenotyping and organ specific endpoints.

Keywords: Sepsis; Flavonoids; Immunomodulation; Inflammation; NF κ B; Nrf2; Multiple organ dysfunction; Bioavailability

1. INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is a life-threatening emergency and is described as life threatening organ dysfunction that results due to an unregulated host response to infection (Singer et al., 2016). It is a significant health burden in the world, where tens of millions of cases and millions of deaths are observed each year, and a significant portion of intensive care unit admissions worldwide is attributed to it (Fleischmann Struzek & Rudd, 2023; Rhee et al., 2019). The rates of mortality due to sepsis and septic shock are still too high despite the improvement of the methods of pathogen detection, antimicrobial therapy, and organ support (Robba et al., 2020).

The pathophysiology of sepsis is defined as a complicated and time-dependent interplay of overreacting inflammatory reactions, oxidative stress, endothelial and microcirculatory dysfunction, coagulation anomalies, and consequential immunosuppression (Chen & Wei, 2021; Singer et al., 2016). van der Poll et al., (2017) indicated that pattern recognition receptors on immune and parenchymal cells are activated by pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and damage associated molecular patterns (DAMPs),

which leads to the release of pro inflammatory cytokines, chemokines, and reactive oxygen species. Later in the stages, many patients lose immune clearance, and they are more vulnerable to secondary infections and lack secondary clearance (Hotchkiss et al., 2013). Chen & Wei, (2021) show that the existing treatment is still mainly supportive, like the early antibiotic therapy, fluid replacement, vasopressors and organ support since several of the targeted immunomodulatory therapies have failed in clinical trials.

Flavonoids are polyphenolic low molecular weight compounds, which are abundantly present in human diet and in medicinal plants (Kumar and Pandey, 2013; Panche et al., 2016). Heim et al., (2002) & Williams et al., (2004) show that flavonoids gain increased attention as possible adjunctive therapies in sepsis because of their ability to regulate inflammatory signaling, scavenge reactive oxygen species, preserve vascular and mitochondrial activities and alter innate and adaptive immune responses. Preclinical trials have demonstrated that a range of flavonoids can suppress cytokine storms, lessening organ damage, and improving survival in experimental sepsis, and most of them have a good safety profile (Bao et al., 2022; Shahcheraghi et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2018).

This is a review of existing research on the effects of flavonoids on sepsis. We describe flavonoid chemistry and structure-activity relations applicable to flavonoid biological roles first. Then, we speak about the mechanistic and preclinical evidence of major flavonoids which have been demonstrated effective in models of sepsis, and their immunomodulatory, antioxidant and organ protective activities. Lastly, we consider major translational issues such as bioavailability, pharmacokinetics, and time of treatment and emphasize future research areas that are necessary to help flavonoid to the bench to the bedside.

2. Flavonoid Chemistry and Structure–Activity Relationships

The typical structure of flavonoid has a common diphenylpropane (C₆–C₃–C₆) backbone composed of two aromatic rings (A and B) attached by a three-carbon bridge, which usually creates a heterocyclic C ring (Kumar and Pandey, 2013; Panche et al., 2016).

The difference in the extent of oxidation and saturation of the C ring, the arrangement and location of hydroxyl and methoxy functional groups, and the existence of glycosidic or other side chains result in several subclasses, such as flavones, flavonols, flavanones, flavanols (catechins), anthocyanidins, and isoflavones (Panche et al., 2016). Flavonoid chemical structure has strong relations with their biological activities. Several hydroxyl groups are involved in antioxidant activity by a direct free radical scavenging and metal chelation (Heim et al., 2002). The presence of a catechol moiety in the B ring and 2,3 double bonds conjugated with a 4 oxo group in the C ring increases the electron delocalization and stabilization of phenoxyl radicals which is significant in redox activity (Pietta, 2000). These characteristics also affect the interactions with enzymes, receptors and transcription factors which mediate inflammatory and stress response pathways (Williams et al., 2004).

In addition to showing antioxidant activity, flavonoids regulate many of the signaling cascades involved in sepsis pathophysiology. Their anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and cytoprotective effects are due to effects on many flavonoids on protein kinases, transcription factors like NF κB and Nrf2 and pattern recognition receptors (Williams et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2018). The flavonoids structural diversity is reflected in the different pharmacological effects of these compounds, with some of them having a selective effect on molecular targets (Kumar & Pandey, 2013).

One of the greatest drawbacks of clinical translation is that most flavonoids have low oral bioavailability. A low aqueous solubility constrained intestinal permeability, high first pass metabolism, and rapid systemic clearance significantly decreased systemic exposure after the traditional route of administration orally (Zhao et al., 2019). To address these limitations, the development of complex drug delivery methods including nanoparticles, liposomes, and micelles as well as the use of cyclodextrin inclusion complexes to enhance solubility, stability, and tissue targeting is underway (Zhao et al., 2019). The significance of chemical structure in determining the pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of flavonoids is thus important in the enhancement of flavonoids as a potential adjunct to sepsis treatment.

3. Literature Search Strategy

A narrative literature search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science up to December 2024 using combinations of the keywords "sepsis," "endotoxemia," "cecal ligation and puncture," "flavonoids," "baicalin," "scutellarin," "silymarin," "luteolin," "quercetin," "isorhamnetin," "fisetin," "myricetin," and "epigallocatechin 3 gallate." Additional articles were identified by screening reference lists of relevant reviews and original studies. Only articles published in English and reporting mechanistic or in vivo data related to sepsis or sepsis like models were included.

4. Flavonoids as Immunomodulators in Sepsis: Mechanisms and Preclinical Evidence

4.1 Flavones

4.1.1 Baicalin

Baicalin (5,6,7 trihydroxyflavone 7 O 2 D glucuronide) is a flavonoid glucuronide that is present in the roots of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, which is a traditional Chinese plant used as a medicinal agent against inflammation and fever (Dinda et al., 2017). Other than its conventional application, baicalin has been demonstrated to have anti-viral, anti-bacterial, antioxidant, and anti-apoptotic effects in numerous experimental animals (Bao et al., 2022).

Sepsis Mechanisms of Action

Baicalin has a wide-ranging effect on sepsis in terms of modulation of inflammatory and oxidative stress signaling, which is relatively coordinated. Baicalin prevents phosphorylation and degradation of I κ B in lipopolysaccharide (LPS) stimulated macrophages, inhibiting nuclear translocation of NF κ B and transcription of pro inflammatory mediators, including TNF α , IL 1b, IL 6, and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) (Liu et al., 2015; Shahcheraghi et al., 2023). Baicalin also inhibits the stimulation of MAPK pathways, especially p38 and JNK, which further inhibits the production of cytokines and inflammatory signaling (Liu et al., 2015). Meanwhile, baicalin triggers the Nrf2/HO 1 antioxidant pathway, resulting in the upregulation of endogenous antioxidant defenses and the prevention of damage caused by reactive oxygen species (Zhang et al., 2018). This dual process of NF κ B/MAPK down regulation and Nrf2/HO 1 up regulation are in favour of a change in a highly pro inflammatory and oxidative environment to a more moderated immune response.

Preclinical sepsis models

Baicalin treatment of murine models of LPS-induced endotoxemia significantly decreased the levels of serum TNF α , IL 1b, and IL 6, inhibited histopathological dysfunction in key organs, and increased survival rates (Shahcheraghi et al., 2023). The same protection effects have been achieved in a model called cecal ligation and puncture (CLP) which is much closer to human polymicrobial sepsis. Baicalin improved the hepatic and renal dysfunction, reduced pulmonary neutrophil infiltration, and prolonged survival in CLP induced septic mice compared to untreated controls (Li et al., 2021).

Baicalin also has direct antimicrobial activity as well as synergistic effects with traditional antibiotics, along with immunomodulatory and antioxidant effects. In experimental research, it was demonstrated that baicalin increases the activity of conventional antibiotics against such pathogens as methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, which may introduce the possibility of using baicalin as an adjunctive treatment in sepsis (Divyakolu et al., 2019; dos Santos Ramos et al., 2020).

Critical appraisal

In general, the preclinical evidence indicates that baicalin is a promising adjunctive candidate in sepsis management. It has a mechanistically appealing combination of strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and organ-protective properties (Bao et al., 2022; Shahcheraghi et al., 2023). Despite encouraging preclinical findings, this flavonoid has not yet been evaluated in randomized controlled trials involving patients with sepsis, so its clinical benefit in humans remains unproven. But there is a lack of evidence in other species, and pharmacokinetic and dosing analyses of the context of sepsis are not well-characterized (Zhao et al., 2019). The lack of clinically tested formulations that can be used by critically ill patients and poor oral bioavailability are significant challenges. The pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic characterization in sepsis models, investigation of intravenous or nano based formulations, and early

phase clinical trials based on safety, biomarker reactions, and organ selective results should be prioritized in future work.

4.1.2 Scutellarin

The predominant active flavonoid that *Erigeron breviscapus* (Vant.) produces is called Scutellarin (scutellarein-7-O-2-D-glucuronide). Hand.-Mazz. and various species of *Scutellaria* (Wang and Ma, 2018). This flavone glucuronide is widely researched in terms of cardiovascular and neuroprotective properties, and the anti-inflammatory properties are being discovered.

Mechanisms of action in sepsis

Scutellarin has anti-inflammatory effects which occur in various ways. It inhibits LPS-mediated NF- κ B and MAPK activation in macrophages, decreasing the synthesis of TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6 (Peng et al., 2020). Scutellarin is another inhibitor of NLRP3 inflammasome activation, which reduces the maturation and release of IL-1 β (Peng et al., 2020). Scutellarin exerts antioxidant effects by mediating the Nrf2/HO-pathway and direct radical scavenging (Wang et al., 2020). Also, scutellarin preserves endothelial barrier activity by lowering vascular permeability and expression of adhesion molecules (Tan et al., 2007).

Preclinical Evidence on Sepsis Models

Pre-treatment of LPS-induced endotoxemic mice with scutellarin had a beneficial effect on the prevention of pulmonary inflammation, vascular permeability, TNF- α and IL-6 levels in circulation, and survival (Tan et al., 2007). In hepatic ischemia-reperfusion injury models of interest in liver dysfunction caused by sepsis scutellarin inhibited hepatocyte apoptosis and salvaged liver function by inhibiting oxidative stress and inflammation (Toklu et al., 2008). There is no specific research in CLP-induced polymicrobial sepsis, however, the existing evidence indicates that scutellarin can potentially prevent multiple organ damage due to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.

Critical Appraisal

Scutellarin exhibits definite anti-inflammatory and endothelial-protective properties in LPS-based models, yet the effectiveness of the agent in polymicrobial sepsis-related clinically is still to be confirmed. At present, data for this compound in sepsis are confined to mechanistic experiments and animal models, and there are no randomized clinical trials in human sepsis assessing its efficacy. According to pharmacokinetic studies, oral bioavailability is poor, and parenteral delivery has been used in most preclinical studies (Wang and Ma, 2018). Before clinical translation, development of formulations that could be used intravenously in critically ill patients and tested in CLP models with clinically significant treatment windows are required.

4.1.3 Silymarin

Silymarin is a standardized extract of milk thistle plant *Silybum marianum* (L.), a mixture of flavonolignans such as silybin (70-80%), silydianin (10%), and silychristin (20%) (Brent and Shao-Nong, 2013). Silymarin is an old hepatoprotectant whose use has been studied in several inflammatory diseases.

Mechanisms of action of sepsis

Silymarin has anti-inflammatory effects related to the inhibition of NF- κ B activation and the downregulation of TNF- α and IL-1 β and iNOS expression in stimulated macrophages (Chan et al., 2015). Silymarin prevents neutrophil invasion and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation as well, which also helps to prevent tissue damage. The polyphenolic structure of silymarin is the reason why it has antioxidant activity, radical scavenging and metal chelation (Kurkin et al., 2009). Moreover, silymarin prevents the destabilization of cell membranes and mitochondrial dysfunction, which could help prevent the damage of cells in sepsis (Yang et al., 2014).

Preclinical experience in sepsis models

Silymarin treatment in CLP-induced septic rats remarkably reduced liver and kidney damage as indicated by decreased serum transaminases, creatinine and blood urea nitrogen (Al-Kadi et al., 2020). Silymarin also reduced the levels of TNF- α , IL-6 and nitric oxide (NO) in the blood and lowered the oxidative stress indicators in various organs (Toklu et al., 2008). Histological analysis showed that there was less inflammatory infiltration and tissue damage in the lungs, liver, and kidney of silymarin-treated animals

having septic conditions. These protective properties were related to the decreased neutrophil infiltration and ROS generation (Chan et al., 2015).

Critical appraisal

Silymarin has shown stable hepatoprotective and anti-inflammatory activity in CLP sepsis models and the protection against multiple organ dysfunction is evidenced. It has a long history of clinical use in liver disease giving it valuable safety data. Human studies with this flavonoid in other conditions provide useful safety and pharmacokinetic information, but they do not establish efficacy in sepsis and should be interpreted only as background data. Nevertheless, similarly to other flavonoids, silymarin is characterized by a low oral bioavailability caused by the low aqueous solubility and high first-pass metabolism (Zhao et al., 2019). Formulations with improved bioavailability or by parenteral route would be necessary in clinical studies in septic patients.

4.1.4 Luteolin

Among the fruits, vegetable and medicinal herbs, luteolin (3,4,5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) is a common flavone in celery, parsley and chamomile (Lopez-Lazarillo, 2009). It has occupied a limelight in terms of its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant as well as anticancer properties.

Mechanisms of Action in Sepsis

Luteolin has potent anti-inflammatory actions in the shape of NF-KB and STAT3 signal pathway inhibition (Chuammitri et al., 2017). It suppresses the expression of TNF-alpha, IL-1, IL-6 and NO by LPS in macrophages and the expression of adhesion molecules on the endothelial cells, which inhibits the recruitment of leukocytes to inflamed tissue (Pan et al., 2022). Luteolin can also induce the Nrf2/ HO-1 pathway which is an enhancement of antioxidant defenses of the cells (Lin et al., 2008). Moreover, luteolin inhibits NLRP3 inflammasomes activation, reduces the maturation and release of IL-1b (Zhang et al., 2014).

Preclinical Evidence in Sepsis Model

Luteolin has also reduced pulmonary edema, inflammatory cell infiltration, and pro-inflammatory cytokines in LPS-induced models of acute lung injury in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (Pan et al., 2022). Myocardial dysfunction caused by sepsis and liver damage in experimentally induced endotoxemia was also prevented by luteolin. The studies concerning the CLP-induced sepsis models are limited, but available information suggests that luteolin helps to reduce the inflammation of the system and harm to various organs (Rungsung et al., 2018).

Critical appraisal

Luteolin displays high anti-inflammatory in vitro and LPS-based models, and there are signs of the existence of various mechanisms, which are applicable to sepsis pathophysiology. Evidence supporting the use of this agent in sepsis is limited to in vitro and in vivo experimental work; robust human data, including randomized sepsis trials, are currently lacking. However, its oral bioavailability is low, and so is systemic exposure because it is metabolized very quickly (Zhao et al., 2019). Prior to the clinical translation, it is necessary to test in polymicrobial sepsis models that have a clinically relevant treatment window and formulations that can be formulated in the acute care environment.

4.2 Flavonols

4.2.1 Quercetin

One of the most common flavonoids that is found in food is quercetin (3,3,4,5,7-pentahydroxyflavone), which is abundant in the foods; onions, apples, berries, tea, and red wine (Hollman and Katan, 1999). It has been widely examined due to its various biological properties such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-proliferative and antimicrobial activity (Lesjak et al., 2018).

Mechanism of Action in Sepsis

Quercetin prevents the activation of NF-kB by LPS in macrophages suppressing IKK or the phosphorylation of I κ B α and, consequently, nuclear translocation of p65 and the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes (Dai et al., 2013). Quercetin also suppresses MAPK signaling, especially p38 and JNK, which also suppresses the production of inflammatory mediators (Cho et al., 2003). Also, quercetin increases the Nrf2 pathway to activate antioxidant enzymes such as HO-1, glutathione S-transferase, and

NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase (Yao et al., 2007). In addition to its impact on inflammatory signaling, quercetin directly reacts with ROS and is a chelator of transition metal ions, which is why it has antioxidant activity (Lesjak et al., 2018). Quercetin also inhibits the release of high mobility group box 1 (HMGB1) late mediator of lethal sepsis and prevents the inflammatory reaction caused by HMGB1 (Park et al., 2018). Moreover, quercetin maintains the barrier properties of endothelial cells by minimizing vascular permeability and the expression of adhesion molecules (Wang et al., 2014).

Preclinical Evidence in Sepsis Models

Pretreatment with quercetin in LPS-induced models of acute lung injury notably decreased pulmonary edema, the inflammatory infiltration of inflammatory cells, and the concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Huang et al., 2015). Production of IL-10 was also enhanced by quercetin, which indicated the stimulation of anti-inflammatory effects (Huang et al., 2015). In the CLP-induced septic mice, quercetin treatment alleviated multiple organ damage, mitigated the oxidative stress indicators, suppressed HMGB1, and enhanced survival (Cui et al., 2019; Park et al., 2018). In Gerin et al. (2016), treatment with quercetin decreased the damage of the lungs to the septic rats with the evidence of better histopathology and lower levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) and NO. Likewise, Wang et al. (2014) have found that quercetin prevented LPS-induced acute lung injury through the inhibition of inflammatory cells influx, the phosphorylation of NF- κ B p65, and the expression of COX-2 and iNOS.

Critical Appraisal

Quercetin possesses the largest preclinical evidence base of flavonoids against sepsis, which have been consistently shown to possess anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and organ-protective properties in a variety of different models. Of particular interest is its capacity to suppress early (TNF- α , IL-1 β) as well as late (HMGB1) inflammatory mediators. Clinical experience from non-sepsis indications mainly informs tolerability, dosing, and metabolism; it cannot be extrapolated as proof of benefit in septic patients. Nevertheless, quercetin has a very low oral bioavailability (<2%) because of a high level of first-pass metabolism and clearance (Zhao et al., 2019). Clinical translation requires intravenous administration or advanced formulation approaches in the acute care environment.

4.2.2 Isorhamnetin

Isorhamnetin (3'-methoxy-3,4', 5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) is a methylated derivative of quercetin which is present in many medicinal plants such as *Hippophae rhamnoides* and *Ginkgo biloba* (Gong et al., 2020). It has proven to be anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and cardioprotective.

Mechanisms of action in sepsis

Isorhamnetin has anti-inflammatory properties due to its ability to inhibit the NF- κ B, PI3K/AKT, and MAPK signaling activities (Gong et al., 2020). It inhibits the synthesis of LPS-induced in macrophages of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and NO, and expression of adhesion molecules on endothelial cells (Dong et al., 2015). Isorhamnetin is also an antioxidant based on its Nrf2-activation and direct radical-scavenging (Jiang et al., 2019). It also defends against endothelial dysfunction by maintaining the bioavailability of nitric oxide and lowering oxidative stress (Gong et al., 2020).

Preclinical evidence in sepsis models

Isorhamnetin also lowered serum AST, ALT, and BUN levels significantly in *E. coli*-induced septic mice, which is a sign that it prevents hepatic and renal dysfunction (Gong et al., 2020). The protective effects were related to the decrease in inflammatory cytokine generation and the inhibition of NF- κ B activation. Isorhamnetin also suppressed acute lung injury in LPS, pulmonary inflammation and enhanced survival in endotoxemic mice. There is a limited number of studies on CLP-induced polymicrobial sepsis.

Critical Appraisal

Isorhamnetin is shown to have anti-inflammatory and organ-protective effects in LPS and *E. coli* sepsis models, although not in polymicrobial sepsis. To date, no randomized trials have tested this flavonoid as an adjunctive treatment in human sepsis, and the available information derives exclusively from experimental models. It is a quercetin metabolite that could have better metabolic stability, although there is limited pharmacokinetic data in sepsis models. Additional analysis in CLP models including proper formulation and dosing trials is required.

4.2.3 Fisetin

Fisetin (3,3',4,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) is a flavonol found in strawberries, apples, grapes, onions, and cucumbers (Khan et al., 2013). It has attracted interest due to its senolytic, neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory effects (Maher, 2015).

Mechanism of Action in Sepsis

Fisetin inhibits the LPS-induced expression of iNOS and COX-2 in macrophages by inhibiting the NF- κ B and MAPKs signaling pathways (Bak et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2016). It also suppresses the release of HMGB1 by activated macrophages and attenuates the effects of HMGB1 on the inflammatory effect (Lee et al., 2014). The antioxidant properties of fisetin include direct radical scavenging and Nrf2/ HO-1 signaling (Gryniewicz and Demchuk, 2019). Also, fisetin suppresses the p38 MAPK/MK2 signal that is involved in the organ dysfunction caused by sepsis (Zhang et al., 2020).

Preclinical Evidence on Sepsis Models

Fisetin treatment in CLP-induced septic mice alleviated liver-, kidney-, and lung damage, decreased the concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines in circulation, and increased survival (Zhang et al., 2020). Fisetin also decreased pulmonary myeloperoxidase activity and inflammatory cell infiltration, which is a sign of protection against acute lung injury. The protective actions were linked to the suppression of p38 MAPK/MK2 signaling (Zhang et al., 2020). Also, fisetin prevented the release of HMGB1 that had been provoked by LPS, and decreased shedding of endothelial protein C receptor (EPCR), which is an indicator of vascular integrity (Lee et al., 2014).

Critical Appraisal

Fisetin has shown good results in CLP-induced polymicrobial sepsis, including inhibition of HMGB1 and modulation of p38 MAPK-mechanisms, which are also significant in late-stage sepsis. Although preclinical studies suggest potential benefit, there is an absence of randomized clinical trial evidence in septic patients, and translation to bedside practice therefore remains speculative. Pharmacokinetic studies, however, reveal poor oral bioavailability and the optimal dosing schedules in sepsis models are yet to be studied. Formulations that can be given via parenteral route in acute care units should be developed.

4.2.4 Myricetin

Myricetin (3,3',4',5,5',7'- hexahydroxyflavone) is a hexahydroxyflavonol which is found in excess in berries, fruits, vegetables, tea, and red wine (Ong and Khoo, 1997). It has anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-diabetic effects.

Sepsis mechanisms of action

Myricetin prevents LPS-mediated NF- κ B activation by inhibiting I κ B alpha degradation and p65 translocation into the nucleus thus preventing the production of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-12 in the macrophages (Imran et al., 2021). It also suppresses MAPK signaling pathways, which makes it anti-inflammatory. Myricetin activates the Nrf2/ HO-1 pathway, improving cellular antioxidant protection (Jiang et al., 2019). Also, myricetin is a direct ROS scavenger and oxidative stress-induced cellular damage inhibitor (Ong and Khoo, 1997).

Preclinical evidence in sepsis models

Myricetin at the time of endotoxemia in LPS mice decreased serum TNF- α , IL- 6 and NO, mitigated the damage of various organs, and enhanced survival (Ozcan et al., 2012). Myricetin also inhibited acute kidney injury caused by sepsis and lowered the levels of BUN and proteinuria in diabetic rats subjected to sepsis (Ozcan et al., 2012). The protective effects were linked with lowering the oxidative stress and maintenance of the antioxidant enzyme activities. There is a dearth of studies in the CLP-induced polymicrobial sepsis models.

Critical Appraisal

Myricetin has been shown to exhibit anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity in LPS-induced models, but not in clinically relevant polymicrobial sepsis. Existing human trials in other diseases support a preliminary safety profile, yet no trials have specifically addressed outcomes in sepsis. It is highly polar and has poor membrane permeability that makes its oral bioavailability low (Zhao et al., 2019). The CLP models should be further assessed, and the formulations should be developed to be used orally.

4.3 Flavanols (Catechins)

4.3.1 Epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG)

EGCG is the most prevailing and biologically active catechin in green tea (*Camellia sinensis*), and it includes about 50-80 percent of the total catechins (Almatroodi et al., 2020). It has been widely researched on due to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer and antimicrobial effects. The green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) has numerous catechins, with epigallocatechin 3 gallate (EGCG) being the most prevalent and biologically active of them. As Almatroodi et al., (2020) state, EGCG constitutes about 50-80 percent of the total catechin content in green tea. This compound has attracted a lot of interest among researchers over the years mostly due to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer and antimicrobial effects.

Sepsis mechanisms of action

In the case of sepsis, EGCG seems to have its effect, in part, by modulating some of the major inflammatory signaling cascades. The inhibition of the NF κ B activation is described as one of the well-described mechanisms. Namely, EGCG inhibits the activity of IKK and prevents the phosphorylation of IKB alpha, which prevents the nuclear translocation of the p65 subunit. Consequently, it leads to the inhibition of the transcription of pro inflammatory genes relying on NF κ B (Yang et al., 2017). EGCG suppresses MAPKs, especially p38 and JNK, and reduces the production of inflammatory mediators as well (Xin et al., 2016). Also, EGCG triggers Nrf2/ HO 1 signaling, which increases the expression of antioxidant enzymes and mitigates oxidative stress (Yang et al., 2017).

EGCG has been demonstrated to prevent the iNOS and NO production of activated macrophage, and prevent HMGB1 release (Wheeler et al., 2007). The compound is also directly antimicrobial against various pathogens and can improve the effectiveness of traditional antibiotics (Almatroodi et al., 2020). Moreover, EGCG preserves the endothelial barrier capacity and lowers the vascular permeability when inflammation occurs (Wheeler et al., 2007).

Preclinical evidence in sepsis models

EGCG improved hemodynamics, decreased iNOS expression, lowered levels of circulating cytokines and increased survival rates in CLP-induced polymicrobial sepsis models (Wheeler et al., 2007). EGCG decreased acute liver damage, lowered serum ALT, AST, and MDA in LPS-induced endotoxemic rats, whereas Nrf2 and HO-1 were increased (Yang et al., 2017). EGCG was also protective of the sepsis-induced acute lung injury and pulmonary inflammation and edema (Xin et al., 2016).

The systematic review of EGCG safety provided by Hu et al., (2018) stated that the daily dose up to 338 mg seems to be safe, and higher doses, more than 704 mg, could be linked to hepatotoxicity. The average EGCG content of green tea is about 70.2 mg in 100 mL of tea (or around 165 mg of green tea per cup), which implies that moderate use of tea is harmless, whereas high-dose supplements should be taken with caution.

Critical appraisal

EGCG has strong preclinical data on its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and organ protective property in LPS and CLP sepsis models. It is an attractive candidate, as it has a direct antimicrobial activity along with the ability to target several different pathways, such as NF- κ B, MAPK, Nrf2, and HMGB1. Human studies with this flavonoid in other conditions provide useful safety and pharmacokinetic information, but they do not establish efficacy in sepsis and should be interpreted only as background data. Nevertheless, EGCG has a low oral bioavailability and dose-dependent hepatotoxicity in high dosages (Hu et al., 2018). Clinical translation of acute sepsis care requires parenteral formulations and optimizing dose.

5. Comparative Analysis of Flavonoid Mechanisms and Efficacy

5.1 Common and Distinct Mechanisms

The above flavonoids have several similar mechanisms that make them have therapeutic potential in sepsis (Table 1). Majority of them suppress NF-KB and MAPK signaling, inhibit production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and stimulate Nrf2-regulated antioxidant responses. There are, however, significant differences in their potency, selectivity and other mechanisms.

Table 1: Comparative Mechanisms and Effects of Major Flavonoids in Sepsis

Flavonoid	NF-κB Inhibition	MAPK Inhibition	Nrf2 Activation	HMGB1 Inhibition	Key Additional Effects	Sepsis Models Tested
Baicalin	+++	++ (p38, JNK)	++	Not reported	Direct antimicrobial, anti-apoptotic	LPS, CLP
Scutellarin	++	++	++	Not reported	NLRP3 inhibition, endothelial protection	LPS, I/R
Silymarin	++	Not reported	++	Not reported	Membrane stabilization, neutrophil inhibition	CLP
Luteolin	+++	++ (p38)	++	Not reported	STAT3 inhibition, adhesion molecule inhibition	LPS
Quercetin	+++	+++ (p38, JNK)	+++	++	Direct antioxidant, metal chelation	LPS, CLP
Isorhamnetin	++	++	++	Not reported	PI3K/AKT modulation	LPS, E. coli
Fisetin	++	+++ (p38)	++	+++	p38 MAPK/MK2 inhibition	LPS, CLP
Myricetin	+++	++	++	Not reported	Direct antioxidant	LPS
EGCG	+++	+++ (p38, JNK)	+++	++	Direct antimicrobial, membrane protection	LPS, CLP

Note: + indicates moderate effect, ++ indicates strong effect, +++ indicates very strong effect based on published literature. CLP = cecal ligation and puncture; I/R = ischemia-reperfusion; LPS = lipopolysaccharide.

Quercetin and epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) exhibit strong and broad anti-inflammatory effects by modulating key signalling pathways (e.g., NF- κ B), suppressing early pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β , and inhibiting the late inflammatory mediator HMGB1 (Deng et al., 2024; Luo et al., 2022). The baicalin and silymarin have been widely investigated in clinically relevant CLP models with the consistent organ-protective effects. Fisetin has proven to be a powerful blocker of HMGB1 discharge and p38 MAPK signaling and this can be especially pertinent when it comes to intervention in sepsis at the late stages.

5.2 Organ-Protective Effects

Sepsis-induced multiple organ dysfunction is the primary determinant of poor outcomes. Flavonoids have demonstrated protective effects against dysfunction of various organs (Table 2). The lungs are particularly susceptible to sepsis-induced injury, and multiple flavonoids including baicalin, quercetin, fisetin, and EGCG have shown consistent protection in models of acute lung injury.

Table 2: Organ-Protective Effects of Flavonoids in Sepsis Models

Flavonoid	Lung	Liver	Kidney	Heart	Survival Benefit
Baicalin	+++	+++	++	Not reported	Yes (CLP)
Scutellarin	++	++	Not reported	Not reported	Yes (LPS)
Silymarin	++	+++	++	Not reported	Not reported
Luteolin	+++	++	Not reported	++	Not reported
Quercetin	+++	+++	++	++	Yes (CLP)
Isorhamnetin	++	+++	++	Not reported	Yes (LPS)
Fisetin	+++	++	++	Not reported	Yes (CLP)
Myricetin	Not	Not	++	Not	Yes (LPS)

Flavonoid	Lung	Liver	Kidney	Heart	Survival Benefit
	reported	reported		reported	
EGCG	+++	+++	Not reported	++	Yes (CLP)

Note: + indicates moderate protection, ++ indicates strong protection, +++ indicates very strong protection based on published literature. CLP = cecal ligation and puncture; LPS = lipopolysaccharide.

6. Translational Challenges

6.1 Pharmacokinetics and Bioavailability

Most flavonoids are characterized by poor oral bioavailability due to low aqueous solubility, low intestinal permeability, high first pass metabolism, and fast systemic clearance (Zhao et al., 2019). Such constraints are especially cumbersome with sepsis, where gastrointestinal perfusion and absorption is frequently impaired and where rapid predictable exposure is required. Nano formulations, liposomes, micelles, phospholipid complexes, and cyclodextrin inclusion complexes are strategies that can be used to overcome these problems and increase solubility, stability, and targeting of the tissue (Zhao et al., 2019). Nevertheless, not many of these systems have been tested in sepsis models.

In acute disease conditions such as sepsis, intravenous delivery is a more practical means of attaining therapeutic levels within a short period of time. Parenteral formulations of active flavonoids should be developed. Also, it is necessary to learn how sepsis-related alterations of drug metabolism and clearance (e.g., altered cytochrome P450 activity, renal/hepatic dysfunction) influence flavonoid pharmacokinetics to optimize dosing.

6.2 Timing and Immune Phase of Sepsis

Sepsis is a dynamic disorder that has an initial hyper inflammatory stage and a subsequent immunosuppressive stage (Singer et al., 2016; Hotchkiss et al., 2013). The flavonoids which have a broad inhibitory effect on the inflammatory signaling can be useful in the initial cytokine storm but can be damaging in case of severe immunosuppression. Many preclinical trials use flavonoids within the preclinical period before or after induction of sepsis, which is not relevant to the real world where patients could arrive at different stages of disease development (Bao et al., 2022; Shahcheraghi et al., 2023).

Future work should incorporate immune phenotyping and test different treatment windows to define when flavonoid therapy is most effective and safe. Personalized approaches based on immune monitoring (e.g., cytokine profiles, HLA-DR expression, lymphocyte counts) may be necessary to guide treatment decisions in clinical practice. Additionally, flavonoids that modulate rather than suppress immune function such as those activating Nrf2 or promoting regulatory T cell function may be safer across multiple disease phases.

6.3 Combination with Standard Care and Antibiotics

Any flavonoid based therapy would be employed in clinical practice as an addition to the usual sepsis management (antibiotics, fluids, vasopressors, organ support). The synergy between baicalin and conventional antibiotics observed both in vivo and in vitro is an example of the potential of rational combination strategies (Divyakolu et al., 2019; dos Santos Ramos et al., 2020). On the same note, EGCG has been shown to have antimicrobial synergy with other antibiotics (Almatroodi et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, the interactions of flavonoids with drugs, the influence on the enzymes of the drug metabolism, and possible interference with the immune response to pathogens require systematic assessment. Flavonoids have the potential to inhibit or induce the cytochrome P450 enzymes, which can

change the clearance of the co-administered medications (Zhao et al., 2019). Besides, flavonoid immunomodulation is also important in the clearance of pathogens and host defense that should be considered with care in infection models.

6.4 Safety Considerations

Flavonoids are traditionally considered to be safe in the dietary doses, whereas the pharmacological dosing and parenteral administration may raise some safety concerns. The hepatic and renal functioning, coagulation variables, and possible disturbance of immune defenses should be attentively evaluated in sepsis models and in the initial clinical trials. High-dose EGCG has been linked to hepatotoxicity in humans, and liver damage cases have been reported with dietary supplements that contain high doses (Hu et al., 2018).

Immunomodulation can also be long term and can influence the vulnerability to secondary infections, which is also a significant factor in the sepsis survivors who will be left with immunosuppression over a long-term basis (Hotchkiss et al., 2013). The administration of flavonoid in patients with organ dysfunction typical of sepsis needs research on the safety of its use because of changes in drug clearance that may cause accumulation and toxicity.

7. Prospects and Research Directions

Flavonoids hold promise as adjunct therapies for sepsis. They counteract overlapping pathways, such as NF- κ B-driven inflammation, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and organ damage (Heim et al., 2002; Williams et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2018). Key priorities to enable clinical trials include:

7.1 Rational Selection of Candidates

Prioritize flavonoids backed by solid lab and animal studies like baicalin, quercetin, EGCG, and fisetin and refine them as top candidates instead of spreading efforts too thinly across too many compounds. When choosing, weigh their strength in key tests, success against complex infection models mimicking real sepsis, known safety, and ease of turning them into usable drugs.

7.2 Advanced Formulations and Routes of Administration

Development of intravenous or nano formulations suitable for critically ill patients and performing detailed pharmacokinetic–pharmacodynamic studies in sepsis models (Zhao et al., 2019). Key priorities include:

- Nanoparticle formulations to enhance solubility and targeting
- Liposomal encapsulation to improve stability and circulation time
- Prodrug strategies to enhance bioavailability and reduce first-pass metabolism
- Parenteral formulations for rapid, predictable exposure in acute care

7.3 Phase Appropriate Immunomodulation

Designing of studies that explicitly address the temporal dynamics of sepsis and testing flavonoid treatments at different disease stages, guided by immune profiling. This includes:

- Evaluating the efficacy in both hyperinflammatory and immunosuppressive phases
- Identifying the biomarkers predictive of response
- Determining the optimal timing and duration of therapy
- Assessing the impact on secondary infection susceptibility

7.4 Mechanistic Early Phase Clinical Trials

Initial trials should prioritize safety, biomarker responses (e.g., cytokine panels, oxidative stress markers, endothelial function), and organ specific outcomes over mortality alone, ideally in well defined patient subgroups. Key considerations include:

- Phase I/II trials in the septic patients with careful dose escalation
- Pharmacokinetic sampling to define the exposure-response relationships
- Biomarker monitoring to confirm target engagement
- Subgroup analyses based on immune status, infection source, and organ dysfunction

7.5 Systems Biology Approaches

Integrating transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic data from sepsis models treated with flavonoids could identify key network nodes and refine patient selection and combination strategies. This includes:

- Identifying flavonoid-responsive gene signatures
- Mapping flavonoid effects on inflammatory and metabolic networks
- Discovering predictive biomarkers of response
- Guiding rational combination therapy design

7.6 Combination Therapy Studies

Preclinical studies should systematically investigate flavonoid combinations with:

- Standard antibiotics (e.g., baicalin with β -lactams, EGCG with aminoglycosides)
- Supportive care interventions (fluids, vasopressors)
- Other immunomodulators (e.g., checkpoint inhibitors, cytokine antagonists)
- Organ-support strategies

8. CONCLUSIONS

This is a review that summarizes existing evidence regarding the therapeutic use of flavonoids in sepsis. It has been shown in preclinical research that various flavonoids, especially baicalin, quercetin, fisetin, and EGCG, have strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties preventing organ dysfunction in sepsis and raising survival rates in animal models. These actions are mediated by inhibition of NF- κ B and MAPK signaling pathways, inhibition of production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, stimulation of Nrf2-mediated antioxidant defenses, and by influencing the immune cell functions.

Several flavonoids have been promising. Baicalin has demonstrated some evidence of protection in clinically relevant CLP models with evidence of organ protection and survival advantage. Quercetin has broad-spectrum anti-inflammatory properties such as suppression of early (TNF- α , IL-1 β) and late (HMGB1) inflammatory mediators, and strong protection against multiple organ injury. EGCG is an anti-inflammatory, antioxidant agent with direct antimicrobial activity and survival benefit in polymicrobial sepsis models. Fisetin has become a powerful inhibitor of HMGB1 release and p38 MAPK signaling and able to protect the dysfunction of multiple organs caused by CLP.

Nonetheless, there are serious issues that need to be resolved prior to flavonoids being translated into clinical use. The greatest challenge is poor oral bioavailability that requires the formulation of new drug delivery systems or parenteral formulations. The fact that the septic immune response is dynamic means that it is important to consider the most favorable period of intervention, and perhaps the flavonoid therapy can be most effective during the hyperinflammatory phase. Strict clinical trials including proper patient selection, dosing schedule and safety follow-ups are necessary to determine efficacy and safety in human sepsis.

Provided that these challenges are resolved, flavonoid could be considered as no longer a dietary antioxidant, but a rationally designed supplement in multimodal approaches to sepsis management. They are promising options in enhancing the outcomes in this complex and devastating condition because of their potential to attack various convergent pathological mechanisms.

Acknowledgments

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

Sara Osman: Conceptualization, Literature review, Writing – original draft preparation, Writing – review and editing. Ahmad Zorin Sahlan: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review and editing. Mazlyzam Bin Abdul Latif: Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

REFERENCES

- Al-Kadi, A., Ahmed, A. S., El-Tahawy, N. F. G., Khalifa, M. M. A., & El-Daly, M. (2020). Silymarin protects against sepsis-induced acute liver and kidney injury via anti-inflammatory and antioxidant mechanisms in the rat. *Journal of Advanced Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 3(4), 190-197.
- Almatroodi, S. A., Almatroudi, A., Khan, A. A., Alhumaydhi, F. A., Alsahli, M. A., & Rahmani, A. H. (2020). Potential therapeutic targets of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), the most abundant catechin in green tea, and its role in the therapy of various types of cancer. *Molecules*, 25(14), 3146.
- Bak, M. J., Hong, S. G., Lee, J. W., & Jeong, W. S. (2012). Red ginseng marc oil inhibits iNOS and COX-2 via NFκB and p38 pathways in LPS-stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophages. *Molecules*, 17(12), 13769-13786.
- Bao, M., Ma, Y., Liang, M., Sun, X., Ju, X., Yong, Y., & Liu, X. (2022). Research progress on pharmacological effects and new dosage forms of baicalin. *Veterinary Medicine and Science*, 8(6), 2773-2784.
- Brent, F. J., & Shao-Nong, C. (2013). HiFSA fingerprinting applied to isomers with near-identical NMR spectra: The silybin/isosilybin case.
- Chan, B., Yarat, A., Akbay, T. T., & Şener, G. (2015). Investigation of the effect of silymarin on the liver in experimental sepsis. *Marmara Pharmaceutical Journal*, 19(1), 52-59.
- Chen, J., & Wei, H. (2021). Immune intervention in sepsis. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 12, 718089.
- Cho, S. Y., Park, S. J., Kwon, M. J., Jeong, T. S., Bok, S. H., Choi, W. Y., ... & Park, J. H. (2003). Quercetin suppresses proinflammatory cytokines production through MAP kinases and NF-κB pathway in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated macrophage. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry*, 243(1), 153-160.
- Chuammitri, P., Srikok, S., Saipinta, D., & Boonyayatra, S. (2017). The effects of quercetin on microRNA and inflammatory gene expression in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated bovine neutrophils. *Veterinary World*, 10(4), 403.
- Cui, W., Hu, G., Peng, J., Mu, L., Liu, J., & Qiao, L. (2019). Quercetin exerted protective effects in a rat model of sepsis via inhibition of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and downregulation of high mobility group box 1 (HMGB1) protein expression. *Medical Science Monitor*, 25, 5795.
- Dai, X., Ding, Y., Zhang, Z., Cai, X., & Li, Y. (2013). Quercetin and quercitrin protect against cytokine-induced injuries in RINm5F β-cells via the mitochondrial pathway and NF-κB signaling. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*, 31(1), 265-271.
- Dinda, B., Dinda, S., DasSharma, S., Banik, R., Chakraborty, A., & Dinda, M. (2017). Therapeutic potentials of baicalin and its aglycone, baicalein against inflammatory disorders. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 131, 68-80.
- Divyakolu, S., Chikkala, R., Ratnakar, K. S., & Sritharan, V. (2019). Hemolysins of *Staphylococcus aureus*—An update on their biology, role in pathogenesis and as targets for anti-virulence therapy. *Advances in Infectious Diseases*, 9(2), 80-104.
- Dong, X., Sun, G., & Luo, Y. (2015). Protective effect of isorhamnetin on oxidative stress induced by H₂O₂ in H9C2 cells. *Chinese Pharmacological Bulletin*, 31, 853-860.
- dos Santos Ramos, M. A., Dos Santos, K. C., da Silva, P. B., de Toledo, L. G., Marena, G. D., Rodero, C. F., ... & Chorilli, M. (2020). Nanotechnological strategies for systemic microbial infections treatment: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 589, 119780.
- Fleischmann-Struzek, C., & Rudd, K. (2023). Challenges of assessing the burden of sepsis. *Medizinische Klinik - Intensivmedizin und Notfallmedizin*, 118(S2), 68-74.
- Gerin, F., Sener, U., Erman, H., Yilmaz, A., Aydin, B., Armutcu, F., & Gurel, A. (2016). The effects of quercetin on acute lung injury and biomarkers of inflammation and oxidative stress in the rat model of sepsis. *Inflammation*, 39, 700-705.

- Gong, G., Guan, Y. Y., Zhang, Z. L., Rahman, K., Wang, S. J., Zhou, S., ... & Zhang, H. (2020). Isorhamnetin: A review of pharmacological effects. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 128, 110301.
- Gryniewicz, G., & Demchuk, O. M. (2019). New perspectives for fisetin. *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 7, 697.
- Heim, K. E., Tagliaferro, A. R., & Bobilya, D. J. (2002). Flavonoid antioxidants: chemistry, metabolism and structure-activity relationships. *The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 13(10), 572-584.
- Hollman, P. C., & Katan, M. B. (1999). Health effects and bioavailability of dietary flavonols. *Free Radical Research*, 31(sup1), 75-80.
- Hotchkiss, R. S., Monneret, G., & Payen, D. (2013). Immunosuppression in sepsis: A novel understanding of the disorder and a new therapeutic approach. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 13(3), 260-268.
- Hu, J., Webster, D., Cao, J., & Shao, A. (2018). The safety of green tea and green tea extract consumption in adults—results of a systematic review. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 95, 412-433.
- Huang, R., Zhong, T., & Wu, H. (2015). Experimental research quercetin protects against lipopolysaccharide-induced acute lung injury in rats through suppression of inflammation and oxidative stress. *Archives of Medical Science*, 11(2), 427-432.
- Imran, M., Saeed, F., Hussain, G., Imran, A., Mehmood, Z., Gondal, T. A., ... & Arshad, M. U. (2021). Myricetin: A comprehensive review on its biological potentials. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 9(10), 5854-5868.
- Jiang, M., Zhu, M., Wang, L., & Yu, S. (2019). Anti-tumor effects and associated molecular mechanisms of myricetin. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 120, 109506.
- Khan, N., Syed, D. N., Ahmad, N., & Mukhtar, H. (2013). Fisetin: A dietary antioxidant for health promotion. *Antioxidants & Redox Signaling*, 19(2), 151-162.
- Kumar, S., & Pandey, A. K. (2013). Chemistry and biological activities of flavonoids: An overview. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2013.
- Kurkin, V. A., Ryzhov, V. M., Biryukova, O. V., Mel'nikova, N. B., & Selekhev, V. V. (2009). Interaction of milk-thistle-fruit flavanones with Langmuir monolayers of lecithin and bilayers of liposomes. *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal*, 43, 101-109.
- Lee, S. H., Kwak, C. H., Lee, S. K., Ha, S. H., Park, J., Chung, T. W., ... & Chang, H. W. (2016). Anti-inflammatory effect of ascochlorin in LPS-stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophage cells is accompanied with the down-regulation of iNOS, COX-2 and proinflammatory cytokines through NF- κ B, ERK1/2, and p38 signaling pathway. *Journal of Cellular Biochemistry*, 117(4), 978-987.
- Lee, W., Ku, S. K., & Bae, J. S. (2014). Vascular barrier protective effects of orientin and isoorientin in LPS-induced inflammation in vitro and in vivo. *Vascular Pharmacology*, 62(1), 3-14.
- Lesjak, M., Beara, I., Simin, N., Pintać, D., Majkić, T., Bekvalac, K., ... & Mimica-Dukić, N. (2018). Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of quercetin and its derivatives. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 40, 68-75.
- Li, K., Liang, Y., Cheng, A., Wang, Q., Li, Y., Wei, H., ... & Wan, X. (2021). Antiviral properties of baicalin: A concise review. *Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia*, 31(4), 408-419.
- Lin, Y., Shi, R., Wang, X., & Shen, H. M. (2008). Luteolin, a flavonoid with potential for cancer prevention and therapy. *Current Cancer Drug Targets*, 8(7), 634-646.
- Liu, L. L., Gong, L. K., Wang, H., Xiao, Y., Wu, X. F., Zhang, Y. H., ... & Ren, J. (2015). Baicalin protects mouse from Concanavalin A-induced liver injury through inhibition of cytokine production and hepatocyte apoptosis. *Liver International*, 35(3), 1035-1045.
- López-Lázaro, M. (2009). Distribution and biological activities of the flavonoid luteolin. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 9(1), 31-59.
- Maher, P. (2015). Fisetin acts on multiple pathways to reduce the impact of age and disease on CNS function. *Frontiers in Bioscience (Scholar Edition)*, 7, 58.

- Ong, K. C., & Khoo, H. E. (1997). Biological effects of myricetin. *General Pharmacology: The Vascular System*, 29(2), 121-126.
- Ozcan, F., Ozmen, A., Akkaya, B., Aliciguzel, Y., & Aslan, M. (2012). Beneficial effect of myricetin on renal functions in streptozotocin-induced diabetes. *Clinical and Experimental Medicine*, 12, 265-272.
- Pan, Q., Liu, Y., Ma, W., Kan, R., Zhu, H., & Li, D. (2022). Cardioprotective effects and possible mechanisms of luteolin for myocardial ischemia-reperfusion injury: A systematic review and meta-analysis of preclinical evidence. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 9, 898.
- Panche, A. N., Diwan, A. D., & Chandra, S. R. (2016). Flavonoids: An overview. *Journal of Nutritional Science*, 5, e47.
- Park, H. J., Lee, S. J., Cho, J., Gharbi, A., Han, H. D., Kang, T. H., ... & Jung, I. D. (2018). Tamarixetin exhibits anti-inflammatory activity and prevents bacterial sepsis by increasing IL-10 production. *Journal of Natural Products*, 81(6), 1435-1443.
- Peng, L., Wen, L., Shi, Q. F., Gao, F., Huang, B., Meng, J., ... & Wang, C. M. (2020). Scutellarin ameliorates pulmonary fibrosis through inhibiting NF- κ B/NLRP3-mediated epithelial-mesenchymal transition and inflammation. *Cell Death & Disease*, 11(11), 978.
- Pietta, P. G. (2000). Flavonoids as antioxidants. *Journal of Natural Products*, 63(7), 1035-1042.
- Rhee, C., Jones, T. M., Hamad, Y., Pande, A., Varon, J., O'Brien, C., ... & Epstein, L. (2019). Prevalence, underlying causes, and preventability of sepsis-associated mortality in US acute care hospitals. *JAMA Network Open*, 2(2), e187571-e187571.
- Robba, C., Battaglini, D., Pelosi, P., & Rocco, P. R. M. (2020). Multiple organ dysfunction in SARS-CoV-2: MODS-CoV-2. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*, 14(9), 865-868.
- Rungsung, S., Singh, T. U., Rabha, D. J., Kumar, T., Cholenahalli Lingaraju, M., Parida, S., ... & Kumar, D. (2018). Luteolin attenuates acute lung injury in experimental mouse model of sepsis. *Cytokine*, 110, 333-343.
- Shahcheraghi, S. H., Salemi, F., Small, S., Syed, S., Salari, F., Alam, W., ... & Khan, H. (2023). Resveratrol regulates inflammation and improves oxidative stress via Nrf2 signaling pathway: Therapeutic and biotechnological prospects. *Phytotherapy Research*.
- Singer, M., Deutschman, C. S., Seymour, C. W., Shankar-Hari, M., Annane, D., Bauer, M., ... & Angus, D. C. (2016). The third international consensus definitions for sepsis and septic shock (Sepsis-3). *JAMA*, 315(8), 801-810.
- Tan, Z. H., Yu, L. H., Wei, H. L., & Liu, G. T. (2007). Scutellarin protects against lipopolysaccharide-induced acute lung injury via inhibition of NF- κ B activation in mice. *Journal of Asian Natural Products Research*, 9(5), 437-445.
- Toklu, H. Z., Akbay, T. T., Velioglu-Ogunc, A., Ercan, F., Gedik, N., Keyer-Uysal, M., & Sener, G. (2008). Silymarin, the antioxidant component of Silybum marianum, prevents sepsis-induced acute lung and brain injury. *Journal of Surgical Research*, 145(2), 214-222.
- van der Poll, T., van de Veerdonk, F. L., Scicluna, B. P., & Netea, M. G. (2017). The immunopathology of sepsis and potential therapeutic targets. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 17(7), 407-420.
- Wang, L., Chen, J., Wang, B., Wu, D., Li, H., Lu, H., ... & Chai, Y. (2014). Protective effect of quercetin on lipopolysaccharide-induced acute lung injury in mice by inhibiting inflammatory cell influx. *Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 239(12), 1653-1662.
- Wang, Y., Fan, X., Fan, B., Jiang, K., Zhang, H., Kang, F., ... & Lin, S. (2020). Scutellarin reduce the homocysteine level and alleviate liver injury in type 2 diabetes model. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, 538407.
- Wang, Y., & Ma, X. (2018). Scutellarin: A review of its pharmacology and pharmacokinetics. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 108, 1382-1390.
- Wheeler, D. S., Lahni, P. M., Hake, P. W., Denenberg, A. G., Wong, H. R., Snead, C., ... & Zingarelli, B. (2007). The green tea polyphenol epigallocatechin-3-gallate improves systemic hemodynamics and survival in rodent models of polymicrobial sepsis. *Shock*, 28(3), 353-359.

- Williams, R. J., Spencer, J. P., & Rice-Evans, C. (2004). Flavonoids: Antioxidants or signalling molecules? *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 36(7), 838-849.
- Xin, Y., Li, A., Gao, X., Wang, W., Xu, X., Yu, L., & Ju, X. (2016). (-)-Epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG), a polyphenol, protects against sepsis-induced acute liver injury in rats. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Medicine*, 9(5).
- Yang, J., Li, Y., & Shi, N. (2017). Attenuation of sepsis-induced rat liver injury by epigallocatechin gallate via suppression of oxidative stress-related inflammation. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 16(12), 2877-2884.
- Yang, Z., Zhuang, L., Lu, Y., Xu, Q., & Chen, X. (2014). Effects and tolerance of silymarin (milk thistle) in chronic hepatitis C virus infection patients: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *BioMed Research International*, 2014.
- Yao, P., Lin, Y., & Liu, L. (2007). Quercetin-mediated AMP-activated protein kinase activation involves LKB1-independent mechanism and protects against hepatic ischemia/reperfusion injury. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 42(7), 1015-1025.
- Zhang, B. C., Li, Z., Xu, W., Xiang, C. H., & Ma, Y. F. (2014). Luteolin alleviates NLRP3 inflammasome activation and directs macrophage polarization in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. *American Journal of Translational Research*, 6(6), 705-713.
- Zhang, H., Zhang, H., Wu, X., Guo, Y., Cheng, W., & Qian, F. (2020). Fisetin alleviates sepsis-induced multiple organ dysfunction in mice via inhibiting p38 MAPK/MK2 signaling. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*, 41(10), 1348-1356.
- Zhang, X., Zhang, C., Wang, L., Zhang, C., & Su, Z. (2018). Baicalin alleviates lipopolysaccharide-induced liver inflammation in chicken by inhibiting TLR4-mediated NF- κ B pathway. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 9, 614.
- Zhao, J., Yang, J., & Xie, Y. (2019). Improvement strategies for the oral bioavailability of poorly water-soluble flavonoids: An overview. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 570, 118642.